

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers,

I am very pleased to introduce the second regular issue in 2019. First, allow me to gratefully thank all institutions, reviewers and authors for their valuable support and work. To extend our editorial board, I would like to encourage researchers with a tenured Associate Professor position or above and a good publication record, to apply for a membership in the editorial board. We are also interested in high-quality proposals of special issues covering emerging topics and new trends. If you'd like to apply to the editorial board or wish to submit a proposal for a special issue, please contact me at c.guetl@tugraz.at.

In this regular issue, I am very happy to present three accepted papers from five different countries.

Jędrzej Bieniasz and Krzysztof Szczypiorski from Poland summarizes in their article research on methods for information hiding in Open Social Networks which include StegHash, SocialStegDisc and SocialStegDisc. Guilherme Henrique Santos Miranda, Carla Negri Lintzmayer and Zanoni Dias from Brazil discuss their research on sorting permutations by λ -operations considering rearrangement models that allow reversals, transpositions, and both operations together. In a collaboration between researcher from Spain, Italy and the UK, Koldo Zabaleta, Unai Lopez-Novoa, Ivan Pretel, Diego López-de-Ipiña, Vincenzo Cartelli, Giuseppe Di Modica and Orazio Tomarchio focus in their research on improving the take-up of e-service usage by citizens interacting with governments by the proposed Citizenpedia, a human computation framework aimed at fostering citizens' involvement in public administration.

Enjoy Reading!

Cordially,

Christian Gütl, Managing Editor
Graz University of Technology, Graz, Austria
Email: c.guetl@tugraz.at